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EVALUATION OF 2022-2024 FINAL ATTESTATION KAZAKH QUESTIONS ACCORDING TO PISA READING PROFICIENCY LEVELS

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Abstract

Reading is a language skill that an individual first learns at school and uses throughout life; it is a high-level skill that includes understanding, interpreting, criticizing and evaluating texts beyond seeing and voicing them. For this reason, it is aimed at raising students in primary education as individuals who question what they read from a critical perspective. International monitoring research such as PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment), which allows countries to see their situation in various academic skills and compare them with other countries, also plays an important role in planning educational activities by measuring students' higher-level thinking skills. In this study, it was aimed at determining how well the Final Attestation Kazakh questions between 2022 and 2024 comply with PISA's reading proficiency levels. In the research, six reading proficiency levels determined by PISA were used as the data collection tool. The documents examined in the research are 51 Kazakh (reading comprehension) questions in three Final Attestation between 2022-2024. The document analysis method was used in the research, which was designed with a qualitative approach. Descriptive analysis, one of the qualitative research techniques, was used to analyze the data. As a result of the research, it was determined that Final Attestation Kazakh questions were generally concentrated at the 3rd level in all years and were insufficient to measure higher-level thinking skills.

Keywords: Kazakh language teaching, reading, comprehension, PISA reading skills.

Introduction

Nowadays, reading skills are considered one of the most important development indicators in individual, economic, cultural and social terms. Reading, which is one of the basic ways of accessing information that an individual needs in every aspect of life, is also the key to success. Individuals with improved reading comprehension skills are more successful at school and in all areas of life.

Reading, which is a language skill that an individual learns at school and uses throughout life is a high-level skill that includes understanding, interpreting, grasping, structuring in the mind, associating, analyzing-synthesizing, criticizing and evaluating, beyond seeing and voicing the texts. Reading, which is one of the most effective ways to access information, communicate, learn and improve oneself, is also defined as the activity of establishing a new meaning. The purpose of reading, which is a semantic activity in which mental inference is at the forefront, is to understand the message that the author wants to convey in the text. Otherwise, it will not be possible to reach the meaning and the readings will remain only at the level of vocalization.

The main purpose of the reading activity, which is an effective process for acquiring information, communicating, shaping ideas and beliefs, and building character, is understanding. Reading is the most basic

way to understanding and learning. Reading comprehension skills acquired at an early age affect an individual's entire life.

The comprehension process, which is explained as revealing what is intended to be conveyed in the read or listened text, is based on the reconstruction of the text based on preliminary information. By voicing the words in a read text, the reader gives meaning to the words in his mind and decodes the message. However, in the process of reading comprehension, knowing the meaning of the word is not enough. Comprehension is essential for individuals to discuss, criticize, question and interpret what they read.

It is necessary to have a critical perspective in order to fully and accurately understand what you read. The most important component of a critical reading is making inferences. Making inferences is a skill that requires focusing on the deep, implicit meaning of a text beyond its superficial structure. The reader makes a critical reading when he evaluates the author's statements in depth, carefully, in detail and with a purpose. For this reason, critical reading is a process that requires questioning, interpreting, evaluating, analyzing-synthesizing and approaching the text skeptically.

Especially today, with the development of technology, the importance of reading skills has increased, and its scope and quality have also changed. Today,

which is described as the age of information and technology, with the changing perception of text, literacy skills mean understanding, interpreting and producing information, especially in digital environments. Although the ways to access and share information have become more diverse, it has become difficult to access reliable and valid data sources. At this stage, the importance of having high-level literacy skills such as criticizing, interpreting, questioning, analyzing and synthesizing, and evaluating is understood. In this context, in the century we live in, the interpretation, analysis and critical evaluation of the information we encounter scattered in various sources has made reading a vital need.

International monitoring research in education allows countries to see their academic skills and compare them with those of other countries. On the other hand, the results obtained from these exams are also used as a tool for countries to improve education and create policies. PISA, one of the mentioned international monitoring studies, is an exam conducted every three years by the United Nations Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) to evaluate the knowledge and skills of students in the 15-year-old group in the fields of mathematical literacy, science literacy and reading skills. The purpose of PISA is to evaluate the ability of students in the 15-year-old group who have completed basic education to use the knowledge and skills they acquired at school in their daily lives.

PISA is a monitoring research based specifically on literacy skills. In the 2022 PISA application, the

main area was determined to be reading skills. When examined by year, it is noteworthy that the definitions of literacy in PISA have changed. Literacy skills in PISA 2009, 2012 and 2015 applications: "students' competence in using their knowledge and skills, analyzing, making logical inferences and communicating effectively while interpreting and solving the problems they encounter in various situations in the main subject areas". In 2018, it was expressed as "students' capacity to use their knowledge in daily life, to make logical inferences, to make inferences from what they have learned in order to interpret and solve problems related to various situations", and in 2018 it was expressed as "being able to navigate in uncertainty by using different sources, being able to determine the difference between reality and perception". In PISA 2022 reading literacy is defined as students' capacity to understand, use, evaluate, reflect on, and engage with texts in order to achieve one's goals; develop one's knowledge and potential, and participate in society. (OECD, 2023). When the common point of these definitions is examined, PISA defines the concept of literacy not only as a skill acquired in the first years of education, but also as an interactive process that continues throughout life, as finding, using and evaluating written resources in order to develop the student's knowledge and potential and contribute to society more effectively. In this respect, students need to improve their reading comprehension skills in order to be successful in mathematics and science literacy. In addition, through various research studies, it should be revealed what factors affect students' reading skills.

Picture 1. Cognitive Processes Defined in the PISA 2022 Reading Skills Assessment (OECD, 2023).

Cognitive processes defined within the framework of evaluating reading skills in PISA 2022 are grouped under four headings: fluent reading, accessing information, understanding, evaluation and reflection. According to Figure 1, treating fluent reading as a separate cognitive process is one of the innovations of PISA. Fluent reading skill, which forms the basis of other cognitive processes. It means that the student automatically recognizes the words and reads the text at a certain speed, accurately, easily and fluently. The purpose of reading, which is a semantic activity in which mental inference is at the forefront, is to understand the message that the author wants to convey in the text. In this respect, the reading activity must necessarily result in establishing meaning. It is not possible for a student who has not achieved reading fluency to understand

what he reads. Fluent reading is one of the most important indicators of qualified reading.

Kazakhstan's failure to receive the expected score from international monitoring surveys such as PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS and its ranking at the bottom is an issue that is constantly discussed, and is also seen as the main reason for the reforms made in the field of education. The research conducted aims to determine the overlap of reading levels in PISA exams with the questions in Kazakh textbooks, the achievements in the Kazakh and Reading Skills course curriculum, and various national exam questions. The common result of these mentioned studies is that reveals that curricula, textbooks and national exams are not compatible with PISA. The results of these studies appear to be an indicator of our failure in PISA. However, it is a known fact that national quality monitoring research in the Kazakh education system

is a fundamental element that directs the learning-teaching process. It is known that students make a significant effort to be successful in exams, which have an important place in our education system, and plan their studies to be successful in these exams. Therefore, considering the success rate in PISA, the issue of whether the quality of the questions asked in national-scale exams is compatible with PISA becomes important. It examined the success of students in Kazakhstan according to the question types in PISA, it was determined that students answered multiple choice question types correctly among reading comprehension questions, and failed in complex multiple choice questions and semi-structured questions. The reason for this may be that teachers mostly use multiple choice question type in summative assessments. Similarly, in another study, in PISA, Kazakh students were asked to use discontinuous texts (lists, tables, graphs, diagrams, maps, syllabuses, catalogues, indexes and text in printed or digital format) to answer related questions while answering forced and open ended questions in reply they failed to reach the conclusion.

The aim of this study is to examine the distribution of Final Attestation questions according to PISA reading proficiency levels between 2022-2024. Accordingly, the study tried to determine whether the Final Attestation questions are compatible with PISA reading proficiency. For this purpose, answers were sought to the following sub-problems:

1. What is the distribution of 2022 Final Attestation questions according to PISA reading proficiency levels?
2. What is the distribution of 2023 Final Attestation questions according to PISA reading proficiency levels?
3. What is the distribution of 2024 Final Attestation questions according to PISA reading proficiency levels?
4. What is the distribution of 2022-2024 LGS Final Attestation questions according to PISA reading proficiency levels?

Method

This study, which aims to examine Final Attestation questions between 2022-2024 in terms of PISA reading proficiency levels, is qualitative research. In

qualitative research, data collection methods such as observation, interview and document analysis are used. A qualitative process is followed to reveal perceptions and events in a realistic and holistic manner in the natural environment. In this study, the distribution of 51 Kazakh (reading comprehension) questions in three Final Attestations to PISA reading levels was tried to be determined through document review.

Documents Examined in the Research

Documents were examined in qualitative research. It can be in a wide range, including all written, visual and digital resources. In this research, 60 Kazakh questions from the Final Attestation held between 2022-2024 were used as documents. Questions of the exams were taken from the official website of JSC "National Center for Research and Education evaluation "Taldau" named after Akhmet Baitursynuly". Since PISA is an exam that measures reading comprehension skills, in this study, reading-comprehension questions in Final Attestation were included in the analysis, and questions about grammar and spelling-punctuation were excluded. In this direction, in the research a total of 51 Kazakh reading-comprehension questions, twelve each in the 2022 Final Attestation, fifteen in the 2023 Final Attestation, and fifteen in the 2024 Final Attestation, were used as documents.

Data collection tool

In the research, the 'PISA Reading Skills Proficiency Levels' form was used to determine the distribution of Final Attestation questions to PISA reading levels. To determine the criteria in the form, national and international reports of PISA research in 2015, 2018 and 2022 were comparatively examined and concrete criteria were determined regarding the scope and qualifications of reading levels. The criteria in this form were presented to the opinion of one expert teacher. Experts were asked to classify some of the Final Attestation questions (10 questions) according to their proficiency levels in the relevant form. In this way, the content validity of the form was tried to be ensured. There are 6 levels in the 'PISA Reading Skills Proficiency Levels' form, which was determined by compiling relevant research and reports and finalized by taking expert opinion:

Table 1.

PISA Reading Skills Proficiency Levels

Level 1	1a	Finds information clearly stated in the text. Interprets and evaluates the true meaning of the text. Can understand the main idea and author's purpose of texts written on familiar topics. Can establish simple relationships between the information in the text, between the information given in the text and the information he/she owns, or between the information in the text and commonly known daily information.
	1b	Can interpret the literal meaning of the text. It can search for and find the desired information in a single sentence, a short text or a simple list. When asked clearly, it can find the relevant page within a few pages of text.
	1c	Can understand the meaning of short and simple sentences. Can read for clear, simple and concrete purposes within a limited time.
Level 2		Can reflect on the general purpose, main idea, and specific details of medium-length texts where information is clearly presented. Can compare claims and identify ideas that support those claims. Can determine the main idea in the text, understand the relationships, or derive meaning from a certain part of the text in situations where there is not much information and does not require much inference. Can find similarities or differences based on a feature of the text. Based on his personal experiences or attitudes, he can compare the information outside the text with the information in the text and establish a relationship between this information.
Level 3		It can also express the general meaning of the text in cases where it is not clearly stated. Can understand the text in outline rather than in detail. Can compile information. Can make simple and advanced inferences. Can compare the perspectives of different authors. Can combine information in the text to determine the main idea of not very long texts, understand relationships, and deduce the meaning of a word or expression. Can reflect on one or several texts. Can interpret texts by establishing relationships between texts, making comparisons and explanations. Demonstrates understanding of the text by associating it with information known or used in daily life.
Level 4		Understands the long paragraphs of one or more texts. Can search, find and assemble information embedded in text. Compares different perspectives. It makes inferences. Questions the reliability of the information source. It determines the expressions the author uses to convey his ideas. Interprets language-based differences in the text. Can compare ideas clearly expressed in various texts and evaluate the reliability of the source of information according to criteria. Can hypothesize from personal information or critically evaluate the text.
Level 5		Can evaluate the objectivity of the information source or content. Can comprehend information that is not clearly expressed in long texts. Can use different reasoning methods. Can create hypotheses based on certain information or make evaluations regarding existing hypotheses. Can establish a relationship between the information in various texts or sources and the question asked. Can distinguish between reality and perception in texts containing complex and abstract expressions.
Level 6		Analyzes long and abstract texts whose expression structure is not clear. Can compare contrasting and similar aspects of information presented in the text and bring this information together. It shows that you fully understand the text or texts in detail. Identifies inconsistencies between texts. Through clues, it determines the source and validity of the information and the inconsistencies between the texts. May use a variety of criteria to decide how to use information. Can reflect on the source of the text using external criteria. Can make a critical evaluation on texts other than conventional subjects.

Source: OECD, 2015,2018,2022

Analysis of Data.

The data obtained in the research were analyzed using descriptive analysis, one of the qualitative research techniques. The aim of descriptive analysis is to present the findings obtained from raw data to the reader by organizing and interpreting them. In this regard, the data are first described systematically and clearly. They are then interpreted and some results are reached. In this study, reading comprehension questions were analyzed with descriptive analysis to determine the suitability of the 2022, 2023 and 2024 Final Attestation questions with PISA Reading Levels, thus determining the level at which each question was located.

Validity and Reliability

In order to ensure the reliability of the data obtained in the study, qualitative findings analyzed independently by at least two researchers were compared during the data analysis process. In this study, the data were analyzed independently by two researchers and the results were evaluated by referring to Miles and Huberman's (1994) reliability formula. Considering the inter-coder agreement value, it was seen that the research was reliable with a rate of 79%. Consensus was reached on all data by reviewing the data that did not show agreement.

Findings and Interpretation

In the research; 2022, 2023 and 2024 Final Attestation questions are classified according to PISA Reading Levels, and the findings regarding the level at which the questions are located are presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3:

Table 1.

Distribution of 2022 Final Attestation Questions by PISA Reading Levels.

LEVEL AND DESCRIPTION	QUESTION NUMBER AND QUESTION ROOT
Level 1a. Finds information clearly stated in the text. Interprets and evaluates the true meaning of the text. Between the information given in the text or between the information given in the text and their own possessions; Can establish a relationship between the information in the text and commonly known information.	Question 14. According to this text, which of the following is his purpose in writing the books?
Level 2. In cases where information is clearly presented, one can compare the information outside the text with the information in the text and establish a relationship between this information, based on personal experience or attitudes.	Question 4. Which of the following has the meaning of a condition? Question 19. This passage is taken from which of the following text types?
Level 3. Can bring together information from different parts of the text to determine the main idea of not very long texts, to understand the relationships, and to deduce the meaning of a word or expression, even when the information is not clearly presented.	Question 1. "(...) it is like writing on water (...) it stays between the shelves." Which of the following is given in order by the underlined words in this text? Question 3. Which of the following is meant by the phrase "spending life in a building with completely closed windows" in this text? Question 6. Which of the following is actually meant to be explained in this text? Question 7. Which of the following means the last sentence of the text? Question 9. Which of the numbered sentences in this text comes after "The most famous of the cisterns that meet the water needs of such important buildings is the Basilica Cistern?" If the sentence is included, will the flow of thought in the text not be disrupted? Question 10. Which of the following is definitely said about the work mentioned in this sentence? Question 11. Which of the numbered sentences above are closest to each other in meaning? Question 12. According to this information, which of the following gives the correct dates of entry into service of the metro lines? Question 13. Which of the following cannot be inferred from this text? Question 18. Which of the following emotions is not included in these verses?
Level 4. Can interpret language-based differences by considering the text as a whole. By taking advantage of the remarkable features of the text, one can identify the expressions used by the author to convey his ideas.	Question 5. Which of the following is incorrect about the language and expression of this text?
Level 6. Can compare similar and opposite aspects of information in different texts and bring this information together. Can find similarities and differences in detail and make inferences.	Question 20. Which of the following is the common conclusion that can be drawn from these three texts?

When Table 1 is examined, it is noteworthy that only 1 question is included at level 1a of the reading proficiencies in PISA. Accordingly, the 14th question in the 2022 Final Attestation is at level 1a. When the question stem is examined, it is seen that the question is aimed at finding information clearly included in the text. The information requested in this question is clearly included in the text. It is noteworthy that there are 2 questions (questions 4 and 19) at the second level in Table 1. When the question stems were examined, it was determined that the questions such as finding the conditional sentence in a short paragraph (question 4) and combining the information in the text with the knowledge one has (question 19) corresponded to the second level in PISA.

The main difference between the second and third levels of proficiency defined in PISA is related to

whether the information in the text is clearly presented and the length of the text. Accordingly, determining the main idea in texts that are not too long, where information is not clearly presented, understanding relationships, and bringing together information from different parts of the text to deduce the meaning of a word or expression are the behaviors expected from students at this level. When Table 1 is examined in light of this information, it is seen that there are 10 questions at the third level. Accordingly, in medium-length texts, questions aimed at determining the meaning of underlined expressions, what the author wants to say, some words and word groups in the text, or finding out what is actually meant in the text (questions 1, 3, 6 and 7) were evaluated as third-level questions. In addition, questions aimed at determining the judgments that can or

cannot be deduced from the text (questions 10, 11, 13, 18) also appear in our mix as third level questions.

According to Table 1, the question (5th question) aimed at evaluating the text in terms of language and expression in the 2022 Final Attestation questions is accepted as the fourth level. As a matter of fact, being able to consider the text as a whole and interpret language-based differences is a skill corresponding to the fourth level in PISA.

In addition, it is noteworthy that Final Attestation includes only one question at the sixth level, which is the highest level in PISA. Accordingly, the question aimed at determining the common conclusion that can

be drawn from three different thematically related texts was accepted as the sixth level question. In this question, the student is expected to make inferences by finding similarities and differences in detail. This is a skill that is complicated at the sixth level in PISA.

When examined in general terms, it is possible to classify PISA reading levels as lower level (levels 1, 2 and 3) and higher level (levels 4, 5 and 6). Accordingly, in Table 1, it has been determined that 13 of the 15 reading-comprehension questions in the 2022 Final Attestation correspond to lower-level skills and 2 correspond to higher-level skills.

Table 2.

Distribution of 2023 Final Attestation Questions by PISA Reading Levels

LEVEL AND DESCRIPTION	QUESTION NUMBER AND QUESTION ROOT
Level 1a. Finds information clearly stated in the text. Interprets and evaluates the true meaning of the text. Can make simple connections between the information given in the text or between the information given in the text and his/her own knowledge. Can establish a relationship between information in the text and commonly known daily information.	Question 1. "... (I) with determination, (II) with (III) that she is proud of..." Which of the following gives the semantic equivalents of the numbered words in this sentence?
Level 2. In cases where information is clearly presented, one can compare the information outside the text with the information in the text and establish a relationship between this information, based on personal experience or attitudes.	Question 2. In which of the sentences numbered in this text is the same figure of speech used? Question 15. Accordingly, which of the following is the equivalent of the word "TATU" in this encryption system?
Level 3. Can combine information from different parts of the text to determine the main idea of not very long texts, understand relationships, and deduce the meaning of a word or expression.	Question 3. In this text, the artist says, "Yes, it snowed on my thoughts." Which of the following does he mean by his words? Question 4. Which of the following is the correct combination of these two sentences in meaning? Question 5. Which of the following is not one of the characteristics given in this text of people who will work on a project? Question 7. Which of the following is the reported version of these graphs? Question 8. If a meaningful text was created with numbered sentences, which one would be left out? Question 9. 'What is the impact of social media on daily life?' Which of the following texts cannot be an answer to this question? Question 10. Which of the following cannot be obtained from this information? Question 11. Which of the following is true about the genre in which this text was written? Question 12. Which of the following is the purpose of writing this media text? Question 13. Based on this information, which of the following can be said with certainty? Question 14. Which of the following cannot be placed in any of the blank spaces in this text, according to the logical flow?
Level 5. Can identify information embedded in the text and organize the text by deciding on the information needed. They can answer questions by establishing the relationship between the question and the information in various texts or sources.	Question 6. According to this information, which of the following is the business plan table prepared by her father?
Level 6. Can compare similar and opposite aspects of information in different texts and bring this information together. Can find similarities and differences in detail and make inferences. Can reflect on the source of the text using external criteria. Can make a critical evaluation on texts other than conventional subjects.	Question 16. Based on this information, a person who wants to show the operating levels of gasoline and electric engines and the charging status of the battery would make a mistake in which of the following?

When Table 2 showing the distribution of 2023 Final Attestation questions across PISA reading levels is examined, it is noteworthy that there is only one question at level 1a. When the question stem is examined, the information clearly stated in the text is expected to be solved by the student with his own knowledge.

According to Table 2, questions 2 and 15 are at the second level. At this level, the student can compare the information outside the text with the information in the text, and establish a relationship between this information, and his personal experiences or attitudes in cases where the information is clearly presented. When the question stems are examined, it is seen that students' questions can be solved by comparing and bringing together the information in the text with the existing information.

A student at the third level can combine and compare information from different parts of the text to determine the main idea of not very long texts, understand relationships, and deduce the meaning of a word or expression. When question stems are examined in light of this information, "Which of the following does the artist mean in this text with the words 'Yes, it snowed on my thoughts'?" In the statement (3rd question), there is a text in which the information is not clearly presented, and the student must evaluate the text in order to understand the meaning of the stated statement. Similarly, in the 4th question, determining the correct semantic combination of two sentences

depends on understanding and solving the relationships in the text. Likewise, questions aimed at determining the type of text and the purpose of writing are included at the third level.

As stated in Table 2, in question 6, which is a graphic interpretation question, the student is expected to interpret the text by identifying the information placed in more than one text and deciding on the necessary information. At the same time, students at this level comprehend information that is not clearly expressed in long texts, interpret it using different reasoning methods, and create hypotheses based on certain information. Therefore, the problem is considered to be level five.

When Table 2 is examined, it is noteworthy that only one question is included at the sixth level, which indicates the highest level in PISA. When this question stem (question 16) is examined, the student is expected to compare similar and opposite aspects of information in more than one text, bring this information together and make inferences. At this level, the student is also required to critically evaluate texts on unusual topics. The question asks the student to compare the information in different related texts and make inferences.

When we look at Table 2 in general, it is determined that 14 of the 16 reading-comprehension questions in the 2023 Final Attestation correspond to lower-level skills and 2 correspond to higher-level skills.

Table 3.

Distribution of 2024 Final Attestation Questions by PISA Reading Levels

LEVEL AND DESCRIPTION	QUESTION NUMBER AND QUESTION ROOT
<p>Level 1a. Finds information clearly stated in the text. Interprets and evaluates the true meaning of the text. Can make simple connections between the information given in the text or between the information given in the text and his/her own knowledge. Can establish a relationship between information in the text and commonly known daily information.</p>	<p>Question 15. (...) Which of the following is the subject of this text? Question 20.(...) Accordingly, which number does the arrow point to when the safe is opened?</p>
<p>Level 2. In cases where information is clearly presented, one can compare the information outside the text with the information in the text and establish a relationship between this information, based on personal experience or attitudes.</p>	<p>Question 3. Which of the idioms in the numbered sentences have the meaning of "sadness"? Question 18. According to this graph, which of the following can be said?</p>
<p>Level 3. Can combine information from different parts of the text to determine the main idea of not very long texts, understand relationships, and deduce the meaning of a word or expression.</p>	<p>Question 1. In which of the following is the word "hit" used in the sense of "affecting negatively"? Question 2. Which of the following cannot be the meaning that the underlined phrase adds to this sentence? Question 4. If which of the following is placed in the empty space, the semantic integrity of the text will be disrupted. Question 6. Which of the numbered sayings contradict each other in meaning? Question 7. According to this conversation, which of the following best describes the situation Arman is in? Question 8. Which of the following is meant by the underlined word in this text? Question 9. Which of the following is the correct combination of these two sentences in meaning? Question 10. Which of the following is actually meant to be explained in this text?</p>

	<p>Question 11. Which of the following is the idea emphasized in this text?</p> <p>Question 12. Which of the following cannot be said about the writer who expresses his thoughts in this way? Question 14. Which of the numbered sentences should be changed to ensure the flow of thought in this text? Question 16. Which of the following concepts cannot be associated with what is explained in this text?</p>
<p>Level 4. Can interpret language-based differences by considering the text as a whole. By taking advantage of the remarkable features of the text, one can identify the expressions used by the author to convey his ideas.</p>	<p>Question 13. Which of the following cannot be said about the language and expression of this text?</p> <p>Question 5. "I am happy to visit Madrid, one of my favorite cities, once again." Which of these judgments can definitely be reached about someone who says (...)?</p>
<p>Level 5. Can identify information embedded in the text and organize the text by deciding on the information needed. They can answer questions by establishing the relationship between the question and the information in various texts or sources.</p>	<p>Question 17. According to this information, which of the following is true?</p> <p>Question 19. According to this survey application, which of the following is absolutely true?</p>

Table 3 shows the distribution of 2024 Final Attestation questions by PISA reading levels. Accordingly, it is noteworthy that there are two questions at level 1a. In questions 15 and 16, the information clearly stated in the text must be included. For this purpose, the student is not expected to comment, make inferences or evaluate the text critically.

When Table 3 is examined, it is seen that there are two questions at the second level. In cases where information is clearly presented at the second level, the student is expected to integrate the information in the text with the information outside the text. However, in questions at this level, the text must clearly reflect the requested information. This does not require the student to make a high-level inference. When the question stems are examined, "3. Question: Which of the idioms in the numbered sentences have the meaning of "sadness"? 18th question: According to this graph, which of the following can be said? It can be seen that the questions ask for information clearly presented in the text. Therefore, these types of questions are thought to be at the second level.

When Table 3 is assessed, it is seen that most of the questions (12 questions) in the 2024 Final Attestation are third level. When the question stems are examined, the questions are aimed at determining in which sense the word is used (questions 1, 2 and 8), for finding the main idea of the text (questions 10 and 11), and for identifying expressions that contradict the meaning and disrupt the flow of thought (questions 4, 6 and 14).

), questions aimed at combining the sentences correctly in meaning (question 9), questions aimed at finding the expression that best describes the situation in the text (question 7), and questions aimed at identifying the expression that cannot be removed from the text (questions 12 and 14). The common point of the texts in the relevant question stems is that they are texts of medium length and do not contain clear information. The fourth level in PISA covers skills to consider the text as a whole and detect language-based differences in the text.

Accordingly, looking at Table 3, the 13th question, which asks the student to evaluate the text in terms of language and expression, and the 5th question, which asks the student to find the implicit meaning from the linguistic expression in the text, indicate a high-level skill.

In accord with Table 3, it is noteworthy that there are two questions for the fifth level in PISA. When questions 17 and 19 at this level are examined, the student is expected to be able to identify information placed in more than one text and to organize the text by deciding on the necessary information. These questions, also referred to as graph or table interpretation questions, are inference questions that require high-level thinking skills.

When we look at Table 3 in general, it is determined that 4 questions in the 2024 Final Attestation correspond to low-level skills and 4 of them correspond to high-level skills.

Table 4.

Distribution of 2022-2024 Final Attestation Questions by PISA Reading Levels

LEVELS	2022 Final Attestation	2023 Final Attestation	2024 Final Attestation	TOTAL
Level 6	1	1	-	2
Level 5	-	1	2	3
Level 4	1	-	2	3
Level 3	10	11	12	33
Level 2	2	2	2	6
Level 1	1	1	2	4
TOTAL	15	16	20	51

When the general table 4 showing the distribution of 2022-2024 Final Attestation questions across PISA reading levels is examined, it is seen that the questions are generally concentrated at the 3rd level. However, when we look at the first level, which is considered the lowest level, in terms of all years, it can be seen that there are six questions in total. The levels with the fewest questions are the fourth level (f=3), sixth level (f=2), 1a level (f=4) and fifth level (f=3), respectively. It seems that most of the problems are concentrated at the third level.

Discussion and Conclusion

Reading proficiencies in PISA are grouped into six levels. The first three of these levels (levels 1, 2 and 3) cover lower level reading skills, and the other three cover higher level reading skills (levels 4, 5 and 6). In this study, which aims to examine 51 questions (reading comprehension) in three Final Attestation exams held in Kazakhstan between 2022-2024 according to PISA reading proficiency levels, it is noticeable that the questions in these exams are concentrated mostly at the 3rd level of PISA. When examined in terms of years, it is noteworthy that the Final Attestation questions in 2024 contain questions that measure more high-level skills. It is noteworthy that only 8 of the 51 Kazakh reading comprehension questions examined in this study were concentrated at the 4th, 5th and 6th levels, which correspond to the upper levels in PISA. Other research results reveal that the reason why some countries have high success rates in international exams such as PISA is related to the fact that students are accustomed to questions that measure high-level skills.

When the international literature is examined, it is seen that there are different studies linking reading skills and PISA exam results. For example, Xiao and Hu (2019) analyzed the educational practices of the top five countries that were successful in reading skills in PISA 2015; It has been revealed that competence in information and communication technologies (ICT) is an important factor in students' success. Similarly, Naumann and Sälzer (2017) discussed the digital reading proficiency of students in Germany in PISA 2012 and revealed that there was a significant relationship between ICT use and PISA success.

Suggestions

Text diversity should be increased in national-scale exams such as Final Attestations. Question types that develop students' higher-level thinking skills should be included with texts such as lists, tables, figures, graphs and diagrams. In addition, care should be taken to ensure that the questions for such texts are such that students can solve them by making inferences, and that the answer is not directly included in the text.

In addition to asking questions in Final Attestation that meet the criteria for PISA's high-level reading skills, students also need to be prepared for such questions. If the student is not confronted with such questions in the learning-teaching process, his success level will be low. For this reason, it should be ensured that the achievements in the curriculum of courses such as Kazakh and Reading Skills and the questions in Kazakh textbooks are of a type that will develop high-level

thinking skills, and studies that reveal this relationship should be conducted.

Apart from the achievements in the curriculum and the questions in the textbooks, studies can be conducted to examine the nature of the questions teachers ask in written and oral exams in the classroom during the learning-teaching process in terms of PISA reading criteria.

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